

Antimicrobial assay on synthetic phenanthridine derivatives

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Abstract : Nowadays lots of efforts have been made to identify synthetic pharmacophores with the aim to reverse, inhibit and retard the pathogenic process. With this regard we have synthesized phenanthridine (PHE) derivatives which are polycyclic nitrogenous heterocyclic with planar structure. These derivatives have been synthesized using Mannich approach where alterations were made between cyclic ketones and aromatic aldehyde. Other phenanthridine derivatives already reported have exerted antimicrobial activity towards Gram-positive and Gram-negative strains. In the present study we evaluated the antibacterial activity of novel phenanthridine derivatives. DMSO (dimethylsulfoxide) was used as the solvent for the ease of solubilisation and diffusion in agar. The minimum concentrations of PHE derivatives used were not showing any significant antimicrobial activity.

Keywords : Phenanthridine, Mannich approach, DMSO, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

Phenanthridine compounds were synthesized based on Mannich reaction. This reaction is an aminoalkylation of aldehyde. Some Mannich based derivatives have antimicrobial effects and also have many biological activities^{1,2}. Mannich reaction is one of the carbon-carbon bond formations in organic synthesis. Quaternary benzo[*c*]-phenanthridine alkaloids (QBAs) is an isoquinoline derived alkaloid widely distributed in Papaveraceae, Fumariaceae and Rutaceae families. Among QBAs, sanguinarine and chelerythrine have structural similarities when compared with phenanthridine derivatives⁴. Phenanthridine derivatives have been synthesized using Mannich reaction and *in vitro* experiments were performed for its anti cancer activity. Their cytotoxicity activity has been tested for various cancer cell lines such as HCT-116, Panc-1, H460, Calu-1 and ACHN which are derived from colon cancer, pancreatic cancer, non small cell lung cancer, and renal cancer respectively³. These derivatives have high affinity for DNA and are cytotoxic towards cancer cells¹⁰. It is also considered to have antiviral and antifungal activities. We have also characterised the favourable structural details⁸. To utilize these compounds as pharmaceutical agents, initially we were looking for the antimicrobial activities *Escherichia coli* (Gram-

negative strain), *Bacillus subtilis* and *Staphylococcus aureus* (Gram-positive strains). *Escherichia coli* are normally found in the skin epithelial cells and gut region. But in some rare cases it is also a causative agent of hemorrhagic colitis and haemolytic uremic syndrome⁶. *Staphylococcus aureus* is usually found on the skin, it is also an opportunistic bacterium which colonizes and causes human respiratory diseases and skin infections⁵. Antimicrobial susceptibility testing is a well established method utilizing Muller Hinton (MH) agar as a nutrient medium⁷.

Experimental

Chemical compounds (phenanthridine derivatives) were synthesized from Organic Chemistry Laboratory (SAS), School of VIT University.

Among the five derivatives, initially two have been used in this study. The structures of these along with the others are shown in Fig. 1.

The test organisms include *Escherichia coli* (MTCC 1701) obtained from IMTECH, Chandigarh, India. The others strains included were *Bacillus subtilis* and *Staphylococcus aureus* (strain NRC-1). These strains were inoculated in sterile nutrient broth and maintained at 37 °C in overnight shaker incubator. After 12 h the cultures were ready for use.

Fig. 1. Phenanthridine compounds structure³.

Antibacterial assay :

The antibacterial activity was carried out by using Muller Hinton medium which was autoclaved at 121 °C for 15 min. The autoclaved medium was poured on Petri dishes under aseptic conditions and the plates were allowed to solidify for 15 min. The culture was spread on solidified agar plates and wells were made using sterile gel puncturing device. 100 µL of each concentration was loaded to each well. Various concentrations of the compounds dissolved in DMSO ranging from 50 ppm to 10000 ppm have been prepared and the antimicrobial activity was compared against DMSO control. The solvent DMSO used was found to have no effect on the bacterial cell growth. The plates were incubated at 37 °C to check the formation of inhibition zone.

Results and discussion

The ability of these synthesized organic compounds to inhibit bacterial growth was checked by well diffusion method. The two phenanthridine derivatives namely **4i** and **4j** among the five derivatives (**4h**, **4i**, **4j**, **4k** and **4l**) synthesized were subjected to minimum inhibitory concentration assay. These organic compounds were dissolved in DMSO (dimethylsulfoxide). *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Escherichia coli* were utilized for testing the antibacterial activity. Phenanthridine derivatives were unable to inhibit the growth in any of the strains, the growth seems to be normal around each well (Fig. 2). The assay has been summarized below in given Table 1. As the anti cancerous activity of these derivatives has been already reported in various cell lines³, these new compounds could be further evaluated for their anti cancer mechanism.

Fig. 2. No zone of inhibition.

Table 1. Antimicrobial activity using synthesized compounds

Compound	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>
	(ppm)	(ppm)	(ppm)
	50 to 10000	50 to 10000	50 to 10000
concentration			
4i	-	-	-
4j	-	-	-

(-) Indicates no inhibition zone formed.

Conclusion

When comparing to Sanguinarine a benzo[*c*]-phenanthridine alkaloid already reported with antimicrobial activity⁹, the PHE derivatives used was not showing any significant microbial inhibition. The experiment was carried out upto a concentration of 10000 ppm and no significant antimicrobial activity was observed. Studies are to be carried out in the near future for a still higher concentration to determine the minimum inhibitory concentration against bacterial strains, the compound being organic in origin.

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